

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUHINDO****FIRST NAME: BENSON****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Deleted: KABIRU

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Academic essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 33-39)
4. American Vs. British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 24-32)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Formatted: Centred

1) INTRODUCTION

My admission to EUCLID was a source of joy and fulfillment after searching and reading to find the right university to pursue this vital step in my career. The elation was short-lived, knowing that the journey would be long and require resilience and commitment. I have quickly adjusted from excitement to focusing on the introductory processes so far. My delayed start to the course due to changes at my workplace not only increased my anxiety but kept me guessing on what to expect once I started the course. I read materials on the University website that gave me a clear view of what to expect once I started. After receiving the log-ins to the Learning Management System (LMS) portal, I read materials that gave me a good direction to start off the course.

The videos about Zotero (Steven, 2021) and Grammarly (Stacey, 2018) have given me a new view of using technology to write essays, including academic papers. I have written references and citations manually or using Mendeley for most of my study life. Therefore, I have to quickly adjust to using Zotero, the preferred software for citations and references at EUCLID. For this response paper, I have read the ACA-401/ACA-401D (PERIOD 1) revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma and watched the Basic ACA-401 tutorial video by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck has guided me on how to

Deleted: ,

Deleted: ,

write a response paper. This course pack includes the citation method, the number of pages for a response paper, how to set a proofing language, the use of UK and US English, the Turabian rule of Style, and referencing. The minor details are as important as the grand things. It took reading the materials to realize that Punctuation is essential and distinct depending on the version of English you choose to use (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 31-32).

My response paper to the ACA-401 and ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack will focus on five key areas: academic essay writing, punctuation, American vs British English, plagiarism, and style guide.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

A good academic essay requires you to prepare adequately and have a mind map of what you plan to write about, even without writing a word. Defining the essay's purpose and the question you are attempting to answer improves the essay's logical flow and quality.

Authors write essays for different purposes. Academic essays are non-fictional but based on facts and answer hypotheses (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024). The essay writing segment has made me realize that writing an essay is not just about writing but mainly about the preparation to write, which will either make the essay better or mediocre. My high school teachers would always come to class to introduce a new topic and ask questions like 'What do you know about the topic?'. I now realize that to write a good essay, I must first and foremost be clear about what I know about the subject, what I need to know, and the relevant materials I need to review to improve my knowledge. I also note that starting to write my essays early enough will give me ample time to review them and refine the logical flow, accuracy, and quality rather than rushing through the write-up without giving it enough time. One way to achieve this is to avoid procrastination (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 11). Writing an essay early before submission will enable me to develop ideas and help me understand them better than when rushed.

Academic essay writing will require brainstorming, which refines the understanding of the subject. Extensive research is necessary to widen this understanding and further develop the writer's point of view on the subject. Several materials are available to read to write a good essay, which can be confusing and time-consuming. However, one can skim through the contents of the materials to identify only the relevant chapters to their subject (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 9). I agree with this argument because reviewing literature requires reading extensively. However, only information pertinent to the subject counts in putting together a good essay.

To write a good essay, one needs to organize their ideas to improve the chronology and coherence of the essay. Some steps include deciding possible answers to the question, selecting information to answer the question, getting examples from the notes to provide evidence, deciding the points to discuss and the order of discussion, and having these points in a sketch (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024). I also learned that the sketch from the points

Commented [KG1]: Always endeavor to indicate the page number

Deleted: ;

becomes the first draft organized into an introduction, body, and conclusion. To introduce the subject, one should focus on the broad issues, then narrow the writing to specific topics and share a summary of what the write-up will contain. In the body, the writer answers the question to the subject using sources to support their answers. Here, the writer demonstrates knowledge of the subject by providing evidence. The last section of the essay is the conclusion, which should authoritatively state the answer to the question, giving clarity on key takeaways and future implications for research (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024).

3) PUNCTUATION

Punctuation is another subject I have not taken seriously as long as the content is explicit and factual. ACA-401/ACA-401D has made me realize this is a key focus area and needs precise attention to detail to write good essays. The general rule is to use as little Punctuation as possible without losing the sentence's meaning (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024). I learned that using Punctuation while writing bullet points requires not putting Punctuation at the end. I have always been tempted to put a full stop at the end of each bullet point. I have learned that this is not right, and I will work to avoid Punctuation at the end.

Cleenewerck & Gulma (2024, 22) guide about the use of ellipsis. Whereas I have seen ellipses in essays, I never thought scholars permitted their use in formal write-ups. I learned how not to use full stops and commas at the end of the ellipsis but can instead use a question mark or an exclamation mark. The pack also guides on not using a full stop if an ellipsis precedes it.

4) PLAGIARISM

Chapter four of the ACA-401/ACA-401D focuses on plagiarism, where writers use information in their write-up without acknowledging the author. The chapter details how a writer can write great work without plagiarism, including giving credit to the authors through phrases, quotes, paraphrasing, and visual diagrams (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024).

It is essential to credit the authors because plagiarism is very unethical and should not be permitted if the world is to get more great writers. I agree that it is vital to give credit to authors of materials because taking credit for other peoples' work will destroy the spirit of creativity, innovation, and originality.

It is important to note that even getting someone to do work for you for submission for academic purposes is another form of Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34). I concur with this submission because many temptations come with balancing work, family, and school for most of those doing adult learning. This habit makes getting someone to write on your behalf to meet deadlines even more tempting. From the essay writing section, I have learned that I can avoid this if I plan work and schedule and start early enough to meet deadlines.

I also note that paraphrasing is preferred to quotations because it is not good to have many quotes in a write-up, making it appear that it is not your work (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024).

I also learned that paraphrasing does not permit you not to cite the author because it will be plagiarism. Some writers have fallen into the trap of this practice, paraphrasing words and quotes, making them sound different, and not citing the authors. Plagiarism kills the originality and the creativity of the writers.

Deleted:

Deleted: ¶

5) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

It is not easy to distinguish between American and British English if you are not intentional or if you are not from an English-speaking country. In Uganda, a former British colony, we use British English as the language of instruction and the national language. Adjusting to American English will require intentionality but will also provide an opportunity to learn British English even more since there are areas. I thought I knew and now realize I was mixing the two English versions.

Deleted: areas

The differences between British and American English can be as minor as the pronunciation, even when the spellings are the same. I have not realized the difference in pronunciation, even as a British English speaker. I will henceforth keep this in mind and learn more about the words with the same spelling and different pronunciations. Words like advertisement, secretary, leisure, and laboratory have the same spelling, yet the pronunciations differ (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024). Interestingly, other words have different spellings but have the same pronunciation. Words like axe, plow, color, aging, cheque, and defense are spelled differently yet pronounced the same. Such spellings and pronunciation remind writers that differences exist and should not be neglected by writers.

The differences can be strikingly minor but essential. Cleenewerck & Gulma (2024, 26) illuminate that some words can be the same but with different but similar spelling and pronunciation. Words like Aluminum will be spelled this way in the American Standard English (ASE) and as Aluminium in British Standard English (BSE). In SBE, this is how polythene is spelled, while in ASE, it will be spelled as polyethylene. The ACA-401/ACA-401D has made me appreciate the differences between the two English versions, which will shape my writing skills as I pursue the course.

6) STYLE GUIDE

Cleenewerck & Gulma (2024, 41) state that a style guide consistently documents the writer's approach. EUCLID recommends using the Chicago (Turabian) style, which is new to me. I have previously used other writing styles and found differences in the Turabian Style. I agree with the argument that there is a need for consistency in the writing style because it makes the work uniform and coherent. I learned that writers use style guides for particular purposes, including technical writing, business, journalism, and web copywriting. It was astounding to learn that certain news stations, like the BBC, use

Deleted: s

particular style guides (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 42). A style guide not only makes their writing unique and consistent even when there is a change in personnel and management.

Some scholars have contested the style guide because there is no authoritative source for written English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41). Because aspects of the Style, like grammar and Punctuation, are well established, others, like sentence length, use of abbreviations, and font usage, among others, can easily be contested. As a BSE writer, I note differences that I would have otherwise neglected and agree that the style guide is important if a writer is to present uniform essays.

Deleted: T
Deleted: is contested by some scholars

7) CONCLUSION

Formatted: RP Head1

The ACA-401/ACA-401D has been eye-opening and laid a foundation for what I expect to be an interesting journey of learning and honing my writing skills. While I thought I knew English by far because of coming from an English-speaking country, this course pack has demonstrated clear differences between the SBE and the ASE, which requires that I am keen enough not to mix the two, given that EUCLID prefers the use of American English. I will use this course pack as a basic reference for my academic essay writing journey, writing as many essays as possible until I become perfect.

Formatted: RP Normal, Left

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 5th ed.* Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Deleted: ,
Deleted: Fifth Edition
Deleted: "
Formatted: Justified
Deleted: "
Formatted: Superscript
Formatted: Font: Not Italic
Formatted: Justified

Stacey Roshan, dir. 2018. *Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium & An Overview of Grammarly for Google Docs.*

Steven Bradburn, dir. 2021. *How To Use Zotero (A Complete Beginner's Guide).* YouTube.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.